

EFFECT OF FITNESS MODULES ON SELECTED HEALTH RELATED PHYSICAL FITNESS VARIABLES AMONG MIDDLE-AGED ADULTS

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Abstract:

The purpose of the study was to find out the effect of fitness modules on selected health related physical fitness variables among middle-aged adults. The investigator randomly selected 45 middle-aged adults men from Trichy city, Tiruchirappalli, Tamilnadu, India. The age groups of subjects were between 35 to 55 years. They were divided into three equal groups as experimental group- I, experimental group- II, and control group based on their initial score in health related physical fitness and each groups consisting 15 subjects. Experimental groups were underwent the training for 8 weeks, 5 days a week for maximum of one hour at morning. The experimental group-I has given fitness module I - boot camp training and experimental group - II has given fitness module II - Pilates exercises and control group was kept in active rest. The selected health related physical fitness variables namely strength, flexibility and cardiovascular endurance were measure by push up test, Sit and reach test and Beep Test respectively. The pre test and post test were conducted before and after the training for all three groups. The collected data were statistically analyzed by using analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) to determine the significant difference. The level of confidence was fixed at 0.05 levels in all cases. The result of the study was concluded that there were significant improvement in boot camp training and Pilate's exercises than the control group on strength, flexibility and cardiovascular endurance among the middle-aged adults.

Key Words: Boot Camp Training, Pilate's Exercise, Strength, Flexibility, Cardiovascular Endurance & Middle-Aged Adults

Introduction:

Research has verified that exercise improve muscle strength, balance, co-ordination and cardiovascular fitness in even the most frail and elderly participant. Strengthening and stretching exercise helps maintain balance and range of motion and are recommended in many fall-prevention studies. Exercise program relevant for the individual participant. Promoting independence and maintain or improving function are two of the greatest benefits and goals of an exercise program for frail elders and adult with special needs.

Boot Camp: A fitness boot camp is a type of group physical training program conducted by gyms, personal trainers, and former military personnel. These programs are designed to build strength and fitness through a variety of intense group intervals over a 1-hour period of time. In most cases, we can expect to do calisthenics, such as pullups, pushups, lunges and crunches, as well as drills and sprints. Boot camp is prepares recruits for all elements of service like physical, mental and emotional. No matter which branch of the Service a recruit chooses, Basic Training is an intense experience

Pilates Exercise: The Pilates exercise method was produced by Joseph Hubertus Pilates in the initial 1920s. He formulated an exercise program with the purpose of growing muscle strength, endurance and flexibility while maintaining spine stabilization. In the last ten years, the pilates exercise method is a popular for body conditioning has better enormously. Several researchers studied the effect of Pilates exercise. Pilates is not just exercise, Pilates is not just a random choice of particular movements. Pilates is a system of physical and mental conditioning that can enhance ones physical strength, flexibility and co-ordination as well as reduce stress, improve mental focus, and foster an improved sense of well-being. Pilates can be for anyone and everyone. Pilates is an exercise system based on yoga principles with Germanic overtones embedded within it. It which mainly focuses on improving endurance and flexibility of the abdomen, lower back and hips.

Methodology: The purpose of the study was to find out the effect of fitness modules on selected health related physical fitness variables among middle-aged adults. The investigator randomly selected 45 middle-aged adults men from Trichy city, Tiruchirappalli, Tamilnadu, India. The age groups of subjects were between 35 to 55 years at random.

Experimental Design: The selected 45 subjects were divided into three equal groups as experimental group- I, experimental group- II, and control group based on their initial score in health related physical fitness variables and each groups consisting 15 subjects. Experimental group I was underwent fitness module I - boot camp training, Experimental group II was underwent fitness module II - Pilate's exercises and control group was not given any kind of trainings. Experimental groups were underwent the training for 8 weeks, 5 days a week for

maximum of one hour at morning. The control group was kept in active rest. The pre test and post test were conducted before and after the training for all three groups. The collected datas were statistically analyzed by using analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) to determine the significant difference. The level of confidence was fixed at 0.05 levels in all cases.

Table 1: Parameters and test items

S.No	Parameters	Tests
1	Strength,	Push up test,
2	Flexibility	Sit and reach test
3	Cardiovascular Endurance	Beep Test

Analysis of Data and Intepritations of the Study: The analysis of covariance on the data obtained on physical fitness parameters of experimental and control groups have been analyzed and tabulated in following tables.

Table 2: Computation of Analysis of Covariance on Strength of Experimental groups and Control group

	BG	PG	CG	Source of Variance	Sum of Squares	Df	Means Squares	F-ratio
Pre-Test Means	7.53	7.27	7.67	BG	1.244	2	.622	.769
				WG	34.000	42	.810	
Post-Test Means	14.33	13.07	7.93	BG	344.578	2	172.289	147.076
				WG	49.200	42	1.171	
Adjusted Post-Test Means	14.33	13.06	7.94	BG	338.9	2	169.48	141.37
				WG	49.15	41	1.19	

* Significant at 0.05 level of confidence

Table value for df (2, 42) at 0.05 level = 3.22 Table value for df (2, 41) at 0.05 level = 3.23

Table 2 shows that the obtained F-ratio value of 0.769 for pre test mean of boot camp training, Pilates exercises and control group on strength was less than the required table value of 3.23 for significance with df 2 and 41 at 0.05 level of confidence. The obtained F-ratio value of 147.076 for post test mean of boot camp training, Pilates exercises and control group on strength was higher than the required table value of 3.23 for significance with df 2 and 41 at 0.05 level of confidence. The obtained F-ratio value of 141.37 for adjusted post test mean of boot camp training, Pilates exercises and control group on strength was higher than the required table value of 3.23 for significance with df 2 and 41 at 0.05 level of confidence. The results of the study indicate that there were significant difference between the adjusted post-test means of boot camp training, Pilates exercises and control group on strength. Since three groups are compared and whenever the obtained 'F' ratio for adjusted post test were found to be significant, Scheffe's test was used to find out the paired mean difference and it is presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Scheffe's test for the difference between the adjusted post test mean on Strength

BG	PG	CG	Mean Difference	Confidential Interval
14.33		7.94	6.39*	2.10
14.33	13.06		1.27	
	13.06	7.94	5.12	

Figure 1: Pre post and adjusted post test differences of the Boot camp, Pilates and control groups on Strength

The post hoc analysis of obtained adjusted post test mean difference between boot camp training group and control group was 6.39 which is higher than required confidence interval 2.10 at 0.05 level of confidence. It shows that there was significant difference on strength in boot camp training group when compared with control group. The mean difference between boot camp training group and Pilates exercise group was 1.27 which is less than the required table value of confidence interval 2.10. It shows that there was no significant difference between boot camp and Pilates on strength. The mean difference between Pilates exercise group and control group was 5.12 which is higher than required confidence interval 2.10 at 0.05 level of confidence. It shows that there was significant difference on strength in Pilates exercise group when compared with control group.

Table 4: Computation of Analysis of Covariance on Flexibility of Experimental groups and Control group

	BG	PG	CG	Source of Variance	Sum of Squares	Df	Means Squares	F-ratio
Pre-Test Means	10.8	11.3	11.1	BG	2.133	2	1.067	.672
				WG	66.667	42	1.587	
Post-Test Means	13.9	15.1	11.3	BG	116.578	2	58.289	52.761
				WG	46.400	42	1.105	
Adjusted Post-Test Means	13.9	15.1	11.3	BG	112.855	2	56.427	62.069
				WG	37.273	41	.909	

* Significant at 0.05 level of confidence

Table value for df (2, 42) at 0.05 level = 3.22 Table value for df (2, 41) at 0.05 level = 3.23

Table 4 shows that the obtained F-ratio value of 0.672 for pre test mean of boot camp training, Pilates exercises and control group on flexibility was less than the required table value of 3.23 for significance with df 2 and 41 at 0.05 level of confidence. The obtained F-ratio value of 52.761 for post test mean of boot camp training, Pilates exercises and control group on flexibility was higher than the required table value of 3.23 for significance with df 2 and 41 at 0.05 level of confidence. The obtained F-ratio value of 62.069 for adjusted post test mean of boot camp training, Pilates exercises and control group on flexibility was higher than the required table value of 3.23 for significance with df 2 and 41 at 0.05 level of confidence. The results of the study indicate that there were significant difference between the adjusted post-test means of boot camp training, Pilates exercises and control group on flexibility. Since three groups are compared and whenever the obtained 'F' ratio for adjusted post test were found to be significant, Scheffe's test was used to find out the paired mean difference and it is presented in Table 5.

Table 5: Scheffe's test for the difference between the adjusted post test mean on Flexibility

BG	PG	CG	Mean Difference	Confidential Interval
13.9		11.3	2.6	2.3
13.9	15.1		2.0	
	15.1	11.3	3.8	

Figure 2: Pre post and adjusted post test differences of the Boot camp, Pilates and control groups on Flexibility

The post hoc analysis of obtained adjusted post test mean difference between boot camp training group and control group was 2.6 which is higher than required confidence interval 2.3 at 0.05 level of confidence. It

shows that there was significant difference on flexibility in boot camp training group when compared with control group. The mean difference between boot camp training group and Pilates exercise group was 2.0 which is less than the required table value of confidence interval 2.3. It shows that there was no significant difference between boot camp and Pilates on flexibility. The mean difference between Pilates exercise group and control group was 3.8 which is higher than required confidence interval 2.3 at 0.05 level of confidence. It shows that there was significant difference on flexibility in Pilates exercise group when compared with control group.

Table 6: Computation of Analysis of Covariance on Cardiovascular Endurance of Experimental groups and Control group

	BG	PG	CG	Source of Variance	Sum of Squares	Df	Means Squares	F-ratio
Pre-Test Means	7.5	7.3	7.7	BG	1.244	2	.622	.585
				WG	44.667	42	1.063	
Post-Test Means	14.3	13.7	7.9	BG	100.578	2	50.289	53.158
				WG	39.733	42	.946	
Adjusted Post-Test Means	10.6	9.8	7.2	BG	95.779	2	47.890	67.188
				WG	29.223	41	.713	

* Significant at 0.05 level of confidence

Table value for df (2, 42) at 0.05 level = 3.22 Table value for df (2, 41) at 0.05 level = 3.23

Table 2 shows that the obtained F-ratio value of 0.585 for pre test mean of boot camp training, Pilates exercises and control group on cardiovascular endurance was less than the required table value of 3.23 for significance with df 2 and 41 at 0.05 level of confidence. The obtained F-ratio value of 53.158 for post test mean of boot camp training, Pilates exercises and control group on cardiovascular endurance was higher than the required table value of 3.23 for significance with df 2 and 41 at 0.05 level of confidence. The obtained F-ratio value of 69.188 for adjusted post test mean of boot camp training, Pilates exercises and control group on cardiovascular endurance was higher than the required table value of 3.23 for significance with df 2 and 41 at 0.05 level of confidence. The results of the study indicate that there were significant difference between the adjusted post-test means of boot camp training, Pilates exercises and control group on cardiovascular endurance. Since three groups are compared and whenever the obtained 'F' ratio for adjusted post test is found to be significant, Scheffe's test is used to find out the paired mean difference and it is presented in Table 7.

Table 7: Scheffe's test for the difference between the adjusted post test mean on Cardiovascular Endurance

BG	PG	CG	Mean Difference	Confidential Interval
10.6		7.2	3.4	1.80
10.6	9.8		0.8	
	9.8	7.2	2.6	

Figure 3: Pre post and adjusted post test differences of the Boot camp, Pilates and control groups on Cardiovascular Endurance

The post hoc analysis of obtained adjusted post test mean difference between boot camp training group and control group was 3.4 which is higher than required confidence interval 1.80 at 0.05 level of confidence. It shows that there was significant difference on Cardiovascular Endurance in boot camp training group when

compared with control group. The mean difference between boot camp training group and Pilates exercise group was 0.8 which is less than the required table value of confidence interval 1.80. It shows that there was no significant difference between boot camp and Pilates on Cardiovascular Endurance. The mean difference between Pilates exercise group and control group was 2.6 which is higher than required confidence interval 1.80 at 0.05 level of confidence. It shows that there was significant difference on Cardiovascular Endurance in Pilates exercise group when compared with control group.

Conclusion:

The results of the study indicates that all the fitness modules Systematic programmes of the two experimental groups namely the fitness module I - boot camp training and fitness module II - Pilates exercise group have achieved significant improvement as compared to control group towards improving the selected criterion variable such as strength, flexibility and cardiovascular endurance. This indicates that the fitness modules were having a positive influence towards health related physical fitness variables among middle-aged adults.

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